

README

There are two data repositories that support a manuscript by Luwei Yang, Callum Shakespeare, Adele Morrison, Andrew Hogg, Angus Gibson, and Brian Arbic, submitted to the **Journal of Advances in Modeling Earth Systems**. This data repository is **Part II**, which contains the data files required to reproduce Figure 7 in the manuscript. **Part I** is available at [10.5281/zenodo.17191318](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17191318).

List of data files

Figure 1

- Steepness parameter: [iFr_4km_SAH_M2_Nbot.nc](#)
- Excursion parameter: [ukbar_SAH_M2_4km.nc](#)
- Drag coefficient: [sigma_SAH_M2_004_1deg_2d_global.nc](#)

Figure 2

- Model grid: [ocean_static.nc](#)
- Full resolution (0.4 km) drag coefficient: [sigma_SAH_M2_2d_global.nc](#)
- 1.6 km drag coefficient: [sigma_SAH_M2_60arcsec_2d_global.nc](#)
- 3.2 km drag coefficient: [sigma_SAH_M2_120arcsec_2d_global.nc](#)
- 6.4 km drag coefficient: [sigma_SAH_M2_240arcsec_2d_global.nc](#)
- 10 km drag coefficient: [sigma_SAH_M2_01_2d_global.nc](#)
- 20 km drag coefficient: [sigma_SAH_M2_02_2d_global.nc](#)

Figure 3

Data: (RMSE) $7*5 = 35$ netCDF files

- 25 km resolution (linear): [MOM6_025_SAH_M2_sigma_x*_RMSE_decomp.nc](#)
- 10 km resolution (linear): [MOM6_01_SAH_M2_sigma_x*_RMSE_decomp.nc](#)
- 8 km resolution (linear): [MOM6_008_SAH_M2_sigma_x*_RMSE_decomp.nc](#)
- 4 km resolution (linear): [MOM6_004_SAH_M2_sigma_x*_RMSE_decomp.nc](#)
- 4 km resolution (steepness-corrected):
[MOM6_004_SAH_M2_sigma_iFr_x*_RMSE_decomp.nc](#)
- 4 km resolution (excursion-corrected):
[MOM6_004_SAH_M2_sigma_nonlinear_x*_RMSE_decomp.nc](#)
- 4 km resolution (steepness- and excursion-corrected):
[MOM6_004_SAH_M2_sigma_iFr_nonlinear_x*_RMSE_decomp.nc](#)

Figure 4

Data: (dissipation) 5 resolution * 2 (wave / bottom drag) = 10 netCDF files

- 100 km resolution
 - Wave drag dissipation: [M2_dissip_100_sigma_nointerp_x14.nc](#)
 - Bottom drag dissipation: [M2_dissip_100_cdraz_nointerp_x14.nc](#)
- 25 km resolution
 - Wave drag dissipation: [M2_dissip_025_sigma_nointerp_x13.nc](#)
 - Bottom drag dissipation: [M2_dissip_025_cdraz_nointerp_x13.nc](#)
- 10 km resolution
 - Wave drag dissipation: [M2_dissip_01_sigma_nointerp_x10.nc](#)
 - Bottom drag dissipation: [M2_dissip_01_cdraz_nointerp_x10.nc](#)
- 8 km resolution
 - Wave drag dissipation: [M2_dissip_008_sigma_nointerp_x08.nc](#)
 - Bottom drag dissipation: [M2_dissip_008_cdraz_nointerp_x08.nc](#)
- 4 km resolution
 - Wave drag dissipation: [M2_dissip_004_sigma_nointerp_x10.nc](#)
 - Bottom drag dissipation: [M2_dissip_004_cdraz_nointerp_x10.nc](#)

Figure 5

Data: 25km (x13), 4km (x10) dissipation, 2x2 = 4 files

- 25 km resolution
 - Wave drag dissipation: [M2_dissip_025_sigma_interp_x13.nc](#)
 - Bottom drag dissipation: [M2_dissip_025_cdraz_interp_x13.nc](#)
- 4 km resolution
 - Wave drag dissipation: [M2_dissip_004_sigma_interp_x10.nc](#)
 - Bottom drag dissipation: [M2_dissip_004_cdraz_interp_x10.nc](#)

Figure 6

Data: No more new data here.

Figure 7

Data: wave drag dissipation in 3 best tuned cases

- 4km steepness-corrected: [M2_dissip_004_sigma_iFr_interp_x17.nc](#)
- 4km excursion-corrected: [M2_dissip_004_sigma_interp_x15_nonlinear.nc](#)
- 4km steepness and excursion-corrected: [M2_dissip_004_sigma_iFrn_interp_x22.nc](#)

Figure 8

Data: No more new data here.